

Derivation and Applications of Fuzzy Slope Position Information

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Abstract—This extended abstract presents systematic research originated from quantifying the spatial gradation of slope positions (such as ridge, shoulder slope, backslope, foot slope, and valley) as fuzzy slope positions information, which were conducted by the authors in the past decade. We designed new methods for solving a series of scientific questions, including not only deriving the fuzzy slope positions information from DEMs, but also applying such a comparatively new type of terrain information to geographical analysis and optimization tasks. Specifically, for deriving fuzzy slope position information considering both parameter space and spatial context, a prototype-based method was developed to derive the fuzzy slope positions information through using those typical locations of slope positions. Then, to fix the practicality issue, an automated method as well as an open-sourced tool were developed to make the above method automated through data mining in a high-efficiency way. To explore the usability of such a new type of terrain information, a digital soil mapping method was developed to apply the fuzzy slope position information to not only purposive soil sampling but also soil spatial prediction. Further exploration was made on the potential of applying the fuzzy slope position information to best management practices (BMPs) scenario optimization based on watershed simulation. The recently proposed methods can innovatively use the fuzzy slope position information to dynamically adjust the boundaries of the slope position units for configuring BMPs during spatial or spatiotemporal optimization of BMPs scenarios, which may support watershed management decision with more practical and optimal solutions resulted from such optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Spatial gradation (or transitions) between slope positions (such as ridge, shoulder slope, backslope, foot slope, and valley) is

common terrain phenomena, which is often related to analyzing the spatial distribution of other terrain-related geographical phenomena such as soil and vegetation [1-3]. It had been proposed to quantify the spatial gradation of each slope position type across an interest area as fuzzy membership values (or similarities), or saying, fuzzy slope position information, for analyzing terrain-related geographical phenomena [2,3] (Fig. 1). This is a typical example of bridging the topographic attributes often presented as spatial continuous field recorded with gridded terrain model and the terrain features often presented as spatial discrete objects (i.e., according to crisp classes).

Figure 1. Spatial gradation of slope positions

This extended abstract presents systematic research originated from quantifying the spatial gradation of slope positions as fuzzy slope positions information, which were conducted by the authors and their collaborators in the past decade. We designed new methods for solving a series of scientific questions, including not only deriving the fuzzy slope positions information from DEMs, but also applying such a comparatively new type of terrain information to geographical analysis and optimization tasks. In this extended abstract, we do not plan to describe the details of

each individual method which had been documented in published papers. Instead, here we hope to bring these methodological studies together to present a systematic geomorphometric research, which may show the value and potential of new geomorphometric method design for not only terrain analysis but also those terrain-related geographic modeling domains.

II. DERIVATION OF FUZZY SLOPE POSITION INFORMATION

A. How to reasonably derive fuzzy slope position information

Those former methods of deriving fuzzy slope positions based on gridded DEM were based on fuzzy clustering in topographic attributes (or parameter space) [2,4,5], or expert-specified fuzzy classification rules within parameter space [3,6,7]. They ignore the spatial context across diverse terrain conditions, thus are unreasonable.

For deriving fuzzy slope position information considering both parameter space and spatial context, Qin et al. [8] proposed a method of deriving the fuzzy slope positions information through using those typical locations as prototypes of slope positions within an interest area, which contain tacit knowledge on spatial transitions between slope positions within the area and also consider both attribute and spatial domains (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Schema of deriving fuzzy slope position information with typical locations as prototypes of slope positions in an interest area [8]

B. How to automatically derive fuzzy slope position information

However, the method proposed by [8] is not easy to implement in real applications, because it needs tedious processes (such as preparing topographic attributes, extracting typical locations as prototypes, and determining parameters of fuzzy inference) which are also time consuming with the traditional serial computing implementation. To fix such practicality issue, an automated method [9] as well as an open-sourced tool (<https://github.com/lreis2415/AutoFuzSlpPos>) were developed to make the above method automated through data mining with gridded DEM in a high-efficiency parallel-computing way (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Schema of automatically deriving fuzzy slope position information [9]

III. HOW TO APPLY FUZZY SLOPE POSITION INFORMATION TO GEOGRAPHIC MODELING

For such a comparatively new type of terrain information, there was bare of direct applications in geographic modeling. Therefore, we further explored new methods of applying fuzzy slope position information to geographical analysis and optimization tasks, specifically, digital soil mapping and watershed best management practices (BMPs) scenario optimization.

A. New method of applying fuzzy slope position information to digital soil mapping

A new digital soil mapping method based on fuzzy slope position information was developed [10]. It applies the fuzzy slope position information to two procedures in digital soil mapping:

1) Purposive soil sampling, that is, using the fuzzy slope position information to suggest those potential sampling locations for measuring the typical soil property value for each slope position type within an interest area;

2) Spatial prediction of soil properties, that is, using the fuzzy slope position information as weight in a weighted-average model (FSPW for short) to predict the soil property values at each unvisited locations (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Schema of applying the fuzzy slope position information to not only purposive soil sampling but also soil spatial prediction [10]

The case study within a small (~4 km²) and low-relief farm in northeastern China showed that fuzzy slope position information on a system of five slope positions (i.e., ridge, shoulder slope, back slope, foot slope, and channel) can direct purposive sampling to collect a few samples of soil organic matter (SOM) content (first-layer: 10~15 cm; second-layer: 35~40 cm) as modeling points (Fig. 5a). In the model-development area, the proposed model can achieve soil spatial prediction result comparable with that from a traditional multiple linear regression (MLR) model with much more modeling points (Fig. 5b; Table 1) [10]. In the model-extrapolation area with similar environmental conditions to the model-development area, the evaluation results of first-layer SOM prediction based on 102 validation points (Fig. 5c) showed that the proposed model was much more portable (with RMSE=1.31) than MLR (RMSE=1.49) [10].

Figure 5. (a) The five purposive sampling points collected at accessible typical locations identified by fuzzy slope position information at 10-m resolution in the case study area in northeastern China (the base map shows the maximum similarity to five slope positions; only one sampling point collected for one slope position type); (b) 48 points for evaluation on the proposed weighted-average model with fuzzy slope positions, meanwhile for modeling of multiple linear regression (MLR) for comparison; (c) 102 validation samples (first-layer organic matter) in the model-extrapolation area (~60 km², within 10 km distance to the model-development area and with similar environmental conditions) [10].

TABLE I. EVALUATION RESULTS OF SOM PREDICTED IN THE MODEL-DEVELOPMENT AREA [10]

Predictive model	Evaluation points	RMSE of SOM (10-15 cm)	RMSE of SOM (35-40 cm)
FSPW (with 5 modelling points)	43 (independent with modelling points)	1.40	1.30
MLR (with 48 modelling points)	48 (same as modelling points)	0.98	0.94
	cross-validation	1.24	1.16

B. New method of applying fuzzy slope position information to watershed BMP scenario optimization

Further exploration was made on the potential of applying the fuzzy slope position information to a methodologic framework of

best management practices (BMPs) scenario optimization based on watershed simulation (or a simulation-optimization framework for short; Fig. 6) [11].

Figure 6. Framework of BMPs scenario optimization based on watershed system simulation

When slope positions were proposed to be used as spatial units for configuring BMPs with more effectively representing the spatial relationships between BMPs and considering the corresponding empirical knowledge [12], more reasonable and practical optimization results could be achieved than using traditional BMPs configuration units such as hydrologic response units (HRUs), farms, and fields [12,13].

Extended from the above method, also with the adaption of a modular and parallelized watershed modeling framework (SEIMS) [14] and an intelligent optimization algorithm (NSGA-II), new proposed methods can innovatively use the fuzzy slope position information to adjust the boundaries of the slope position units as spatial units for configuring BMPs during spatial optimization of BMPs scenarios (Fig. 7) [11].

Figure 7. Schema of applying the fuzzy slope position information to adjusting the boundaries of the slope position units for configuring BMPs during BMPs scenarios optimization [11]

A case study was conducted in a small, typical red-soil hilly watershed (~5.4 km²) in Southeastern China. Four BMPs (i.e., closing measures, arbor-bush-herb mixed plantation, low-quality forest improvement, and orchard improvement) were considered for the watershed management goal of maximizing the soil erosion reduction rate and minimizing the investment. The results showed that using such boundary-adaptive BMP configuration units with fuzzy information at 10-m resolution on three slope position types (i.e., ridge, backslope, and valley; Fig. 8a) in the case study area can enlarge the search space and thus achieve optimal BMP scenarios with better cost effectiveness (i.e., better near-optimal Pareto solutions) than the traditional way of using boundary-fixed units (Fig. 8b) [11].

Figure 8. (a) Fuzzy slope positions maps in the case study area in southeastern China; and (b) Near-optimal Pareto solutions of BMP scenario optimization with three ways respectively (ADAPTUNIT: the proposed boundary-adaptive BMP configuration units with fuzzy slope position information; FIXEDUNIT: the traditional way of using boundary-fixed units; FIXEDUNIT+DYN: first using boundary-fixed units and then further using the proposed boundary-adaptive optimization) [11]

The adoption of fuzzy slope position information for boundary-adaptive configuration units can further support spatiotemporal optimization for optimal BMPs scenarios [15], which may support watershed management decision with more practical solutions [15,16].

IV. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSIONS

This extended abstract presents systematic research originated from quantifying the spatial transitions between slope positions to be fuzzy slope positions information, which were conducted by the authors and their collaborators in past decade. We designed new methods for solving a series of scientific questions on not only deriving the fuzzy slope positions information from gridded DEM, but also applying such a comparatively new type of terrain information to geographical analysis and optimization tasks. We hope such a systematic presentation on these researches may show the values and potential of new geomorphometric method design for not only terrain analysis but also those terrain-related geographic modeling domains.

Future research may include method research on how to effectively combine fuzzy slope position information (as a typical multiple-layer dataset with interplayed semantics) with other often used topographic attributes for terrain-related geographic analysis and modeling, such as detailedly geomorphic unit identification or classification, and large-area spatial prediction on geographic phenomena (soil variation, vegetation distribution, landslide susceptibility, etc.) for spatial decision-making support.

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